

TOR DECOMPOSITION OF $bu_{p*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$

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ABSTRACT. We decompose $bu_{p*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$, the connective unitary K -theory with p -adic coefficients of the n -fold smash product of the classifying space for the cyclic group of prime order p , as a direct sum of some graded groups, which include the graded groups $bu_{p*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)$ and $Tor_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]}^1(bu_{p*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p), bu_{p*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)[-1])$. We deal with the results in [6, Theorem 3.8] together with the Künneth sequence for $bu_{p*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$, to explain that there is no extension problem for this Künneth sequence, for any finite number n not just for $n = 2$ and therefore the middle term of this sequence is a direct sum of the left and the right side.

Keywords: The connective unitary K -theory; a Künneth formula short exact sequence.

1. Introduction

Let bu_* denote connective unitary K -homology on the stable homotopy category of CW spectra [1] so that if X is a space without a basepoint its unreduced bu -homology is $bu_*(\Sigma^\infty X_+)$, the homology of the suspension spectrum of the disjoint union of X with a base-point. In particular $bu_*(\Sigma^\infty S^0) = \mathbb{Z}[u]$ where $\deg(u) = 2$.

For a prime number p , we have bu_p , the connective unitary K -theory with p -adic integer coefficients $\mathbb{Z}_p$, where $bu_p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i-2} lu$, lu the Adams summand such that $bu_{p*}(S^0) \cong \bigoplus_{i=1}^{p-1} lu_{*-2i+2}(S^0)$, $lu_*(S^0) \cong \mathbb{Z}_p[u^{p-1}] \cong \mathbb{Z}_p[v]$ and $\deg(v) = 2(p-1)$.

In §2 we deal with the results in [6, Lemma 3.4], together with the Künneth sequence for $bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\wedge n}$, to explain that there is no extension problem for this Künneth sequence, for any finite number n not just for $n = 2$ and therefore the middle term of this sequence is a direct sum of the left and the right side. From this we will decompose $bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\wedge n}$ as a direct sum of some graded groups.

For any prime p , In §3 we use the splitting $bu_p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i-2} lu$ and the Holzsager splitting [3] $B\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} B_i$ to decompose $bu_{p*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$ as a direct sum of some graded groups. This decomposition agreed with the result in [6, Theorem 3.8] and both also yield that there is no extension problems in the Künneth sequence for $bu_{p*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$.

In this section we fix some notations that we will use for this paper and introduce some binomial coefficient identities which will support our calculation.

Notation 1.1.

- For $n \geq 1$, in §2, we write P_n for $(B\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\wedge n}$, the n -fold smash product of $B\mathbb{Z}/2$. In particular, $P_1 = B\mathbb{Z}/2$, whereas in §3, we write P_n for $(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$
- we write A_* for $bu_*(P_1)$.
- For a $\mathbb{Z}$ -graded group B_* , we write $B_*[n]$ for the graded group with $B_j[n] = B_{j+n}$, so that $bu_*(X)[-1] = bu_{*-1}(X)$.

Lemma 1.2. [2]. For any $j, k, m, n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, we have

- (i) $\binom{n}{k} = 0$ if n and k both are not integers or if $n < k$,

- (ii) $\sum_{0 \leq k \leq n} \binom{n}{k} = 2^n$,
- (iii) $\sum_{0 \leq k \leq n} \binom{k}{m} = \binom{n+1}{m+1}$, and
- (iv) $\sum_{0 \leq k \leq n} \binom{k}{j} \binom{n-k}{m-j} = \binom{n+1}{m+1}$, where $0 \leq j \leq m \leq n$. □

2. Tor decomposition of $bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\wedge n}$

2.1. For $p = 2$, in this section we will decompose $bu_*(P_n)$ as a direct sum of some graded groups, which include the graded groups $Tor_{\mathbb{Z}_2[u]}^1(bu_*(P_1), bu_*(P_1))[-1]$ and $bu_*(P_1)$.

Definition 2.2.

Let X be a graded group, and $r \geq 0$. We define $T^r(X)_*$ as

$$T^r(X)_* = T(T^{r-1}(X)_*)_*$$

where $T^0(X)_* = X$ and $T^1(X)_* = T(X)_* = Tor_{\mathbb{Z}_2[u]}^1(A_*, X)[-1]$.

From this definition we can deduce that:

- (1) $T^r(X)_* = T^m(T^k(X)_*)_*$, for $m + k = r$.
- (2) We have $T^r(A_*)_* = \overbrace{T(T(\dots T(A_*)_* \dots)_*)_*}^{r \text{ times}}$, where, by [7] §2.7, $T(A_*)_*$ is non-zero just in degrees $2t + 1 \geq 3$. Then, by applying $T(A_*)_* \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_2[u]} -$ instead of $A_* \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_2[u]} -$ to the free resolution of A_* , which is described in [7] Example 2.9, with shifting by (-1) and by using induction on r , we can calculate the graded group $T^r(A_*)_*$. This is non-zero just in degrees $2t + 1$ for $t \geq r$.

Notation 2.3. For the rest of this section, we will write:

- A_*^r for $A_*^{\otimes r}$, the tensor of A_* with itself over $\mathbb{Z}_2[u]$ r -times,
- $A_* \otimes B_*$ for $A_* \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_2[u]} B_*$, for a $\mathbb{Z}_2[u]$ -module B_* , and
- $T_*^{j_r, j_{r-1}, \dots, j_1}$ for $T^{j_r}(A_* \otimes T^{j_{r-1}}(A_* \otimes T^{j_{r-2}}(\dots T^{j_2}(A_* \otimes T^{j_1}(A_*)_* \dots)_*)_*)_*$, where $j_i \in \mathbb{N}_0$.

Definition 2.4. Let $0 \leq k \leq n - 1$, we define the weight k iterated T as

$$W_n^k = \bigoplus_{\sum j_i = k} T_*^{j_{n-k}, j_{n-k-1}, \dots, j_1}$$

where $j_i \in \mathbb{N}_0$.

We will see later, in 3.8, that $bu_*(P_n)$ decomposes as a sum over the W_n^k 's. It is easy to check that:

- (i) $W_n^k = 0$, for $k \geq n$,
- (ii) $W_n^{n-1} = T_*^{n-1}$, $W_n^0 = A_*^n$, and
- (iii) $W_{n+1}^k = (A_* \otimes W_n^k) \oplus T(W_n^{k-1})$ for $0 \leq k \leq n$.

Since W_n^k is constructed from the graded groups $T_*^{j_{n-k}, j_{n-k-1}, \dots, j_1}$, then to calculate W_n^k as a group we need to calculate each summand as a group. Let us start with the higher 2-torsion when $k = n - 1$.

Notation 2.5. In this section to simplify the indices in some formulas, we need to change the indexing conventions in the resolution in [7] to be in the form

$$0 \longrightarrow \bigoplus_{j_i > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_i} \rangle \xrightarrow{d} \bigoplus_{j_i > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle b_{j_i} \rangle \longrightarrow A_* \longrightarrow 0$$

where a_{j_i} and b_{j_i} are in degree $2j_i - 1$ and $d(a_{j_i}) = 2b_{j_i} - ub_{j_i-2}$.

Proposition 2.6. For $n \geq 0, t \geq n,$

$$T_{2t+1}^n \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{t+1-n} \langle \sum_{i+\sum_{k=1}^n j_k=t} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n} \rangle,$$

where we have the short exact sequence

$$0 \longrightarrow \oplus_{j_i>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_i} \rangle \xrightarrow{d} \oplus_{j_i>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle b_{j_i} \rangle \longrightarrow A_* \longrightarrow 0$$

as in 2.5, and $v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n}$ refers to

$$v_{2i+1} \otimes a_{j_1} \otimes a_{j_2} \dots \otimes a_{j_n} \in A_* \otimes (\oplus_{j_1>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_1} \rangle) \otimes (\oplus_{j_2>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_2} \rangle) \dots \otimes (\oplus_{j_n>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_n} \rangle).$$

Proof The proof is by induction on n , where the case $n = 1$ is described in [7] and agrees with the above statement. For $n = 2$, let us consider the same free resolution of A_* after applying $(T_* \otimes -)$ and shifting by (-1) . We have $T_*^2 \subset T_* \otimes (\oplus_{j_2>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_2} \rangle)$, where $T_{2\ell+1}^2 \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^\ell \langle \sum_{i+j_1=\ell} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} \rangle$ for $\ell \geq 1$. Then by the same calculation as for T_* , see [7], we can calculate that, for $t \geq 2$, T_{2t+1}^2 is a group with generator $\sum_{i+j_1=\ell} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2}$, where $\ell + j_2 = t$. This generator can be written as $\sum_{i+j_1+j_2=t} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2}$, which contains a summand $v_{2(t-2)+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2}$, with $j_1 = j_2 = 1$ and $v_{2(t-2)+1} \in A_{2(t-2)+1} \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-1}$, see [7] for $p = 2$. Therefore $T_{2t+1}^2 \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-1} \langle \sum_{i+j_1+j_2=t} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \rangle$. Now assume that the statement is true for n . Again using the same free resolution of A_* , and applying $(T_*^n \otimes -)$ with shifting by (-1) , we have, $T_*^{n+1} \subset T_*^n \otimes \oplus_{j_{n+1}>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_{n+1}} \rangle$, where $T_{2\ell+1}^n \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{\ell+1-n} \langle \sum_{i+\sum_{k=1}^n j_k=\ell} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n} \rangle$ for $\ell \geq n$. Similarly to the case $n = 2$ above, where $T_*^{n+1} = T(T_*^n)$, we can calculate the generator of the group T_{2t+1}^{n+1} , for $t \geq n + 1$, to be $\sum_{i+\sum_{k=1}^n j_k=\ell} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n} a_{j_{n+1}}$, where $\ell + j_{n+1} = t$. This generator can be written as $\sum_{i+\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} j_k=t} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n} a_{j_{n+1}}$ where, for $j_k = 1, k = 1, 2, \dots, n + 1$, this sum has a summand of the form $v_{2(t-n-1)+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_{n+1}}$. Again [7], for $p = 2$, implies that $T_{2t+1}^{n+1} \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-n} \langle \sum_{i+\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} j_k=t} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_{n+1}} \rangle$. □

Lemma 2.7.

Let X_* be a $\mathbb{Z}_2[u]$ -module such that u acts trivially on $A_* \otimes X_*$. Then u also acts trivially on $T(A_* \otimes X_*)$.

Proof From 2.6, we have an inclusion of $\mathbb{Z}_2[u]$ -modules, $T(A_* \otimes X_*) \subset A_* \otimes X_* \otimes (\oplus_{j>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_1} \rangle)$, where the right hand side is a graded group generated by $\{v \otimes x \otimes a_{j_1}\}$, for $v \otimes x \in A_* \otimes X_*$. By the action of u on $A_* \otimes X_*$, we deduce that u also acts trivially on $A_* \otimes X_* \otimes (\oplus_{j>0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_1} \rangle)$. □

Lemma 2.8. Let $0 \leq k \leq n - 1$. With the exceptions of A_* and T_*^n , each summand of W_n^k is a graded $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space, on which u acts trivially.

Proof By 2.6 and [7], we know that A_* and T_*^n consist of higher 2-torsion groups with non-trivial action of u , where $uv_{2i-1} = 2v_{2i+1}$ and $v_{2i+1} \in A_*$ of degree $2i + 1$. Now let us consider the summand $T_*^{0,n}$ of W_n^k . By 2.7, the results for the other summands are analogous.

By 2.6, any $x \in T_{2t}^{0,n} = \oplus_{t=\ell+s+1} A_{2\ell+1} \otimes T_{2s+1}^n$ can be written as a linear combination of

$$v_{2\ell+1} \otimes \sum_{i+\sum_{k=1}^n j_k=s} v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n} = \sum_{i+\ell+\sum_{k=1}^n j_k=t-1} v_{2\ell+1} \otimes v_{2i+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n}.$$

And by [7], we have

$$2v_{2\ell+1} \otimes v_{2i+1} = uv_{2\ell-1} \otimes v_{2i+1} = 2v_{2\ell-1} \otimes v_{2i+3} = \dots = 2v_1 \otimes v_{2i+2\ell+1} = 0,$$

and

$$uv_{2\ell+1} \otimes v_{2i+1} = 2v_{2\ell+3} \otimes v_{2i+1} = uv_{2\ell+3} \otimes v_{2i-1} = \dots = 2v_{2\ell+2i+3} \otimes v_1 = 0.$$

This shows that $T_*^{0,n}$ is an $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space with a trivial action of u .

From the definition of W_n^k , we can recognise that any element of the summands of W_n^k can be written as a linear combination of a product of $(n - k)$ v_i 's with some a_{j_i} 's. Therefore, by the action of u on A_* , we can prove the required result for the other summands of W_n^k in exactly the same way. $\square$

Notation 2.9. For the rest of our calculations we will write $(\mathbb{Z}/2)^a$ for a -times the direct sum of $\mathbb{Z}/2$ with itself.

By 2.6 and 2.8, we can deduce the following result.

Corollary 2.10. Let $n \geq 0$ and $s \geq 2n + 2$. Then

$$T_s^{0,n} \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{t-n}, & \text{when } s = 2t, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof $T_{2t}^{0,n}$ is an $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space with basis $\{v_{2i+1} \otimes x_{2(t-i-1)+1} : i = 0, 1, \dots, t-n-1\}$, where $x_{2(t-i-1)+1} = \sum_{\ell + \sum_{k=1}^n j_k = t-i-1} v_{2\ell+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n} \in T_{2(t-i-1)+1}^n$. The number of summands $t - n$ comes from the dimension of this basis. $\square$

By 2.8, for $n > 1$, we know that the only summand of W_n^k with higher 2-torsion is calculated in 2.6. Now by using some binomial identities given in 1.2 we are going to calculate the rest of the summands, where all of them are graded $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector spaces.

Proposition 2.11. Let $s \geq 2j_1 + 2j_2 + 2$, we have

$$T_s^{j_2, j_1} \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-j_1}{j_2+1}}, & \text{when } s = 2t, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof The proof is by induction on j_2 , where the case $j_2 = 0$ is considered in 2.10. Let assume that the statement is true for $j_2 - 1$, where $T_*^{j_2, j_1} = T(T_*^{j_2-1, j_1})$. Now 2.8 shows that $T_*^{j_2-1, j_1}$ is an $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space with a trivial action of u . Then

$$T_*^{j_2, j_1} = \ker(I \otimes d) = T_*^{j_2-1, j_1} \otimes (\oplus_{j_k > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_k} \rangle)[-1],$$

where $I = id_{T_*^{j_2-1, j_1}}$ and $d : \oplus_{j_k > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_k} \rangle \rightarrow \oplus_{j_k > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle b_{j_k} \rangle$ is described in 2.5. Therefore, for $t \geq j_1 + j_2 + 1$, $i \geq j_1 + j_2$ and $j > 0$, and by the binomial identity in 1.2(ii), we have

$$T_{2t}^{j_2, j_1} = \oplus_{t=i+j_k} T_{2i}^{j_2-1, j_1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} \mathbb{Z} \{a_{j_k}\} \cong \oplus_{t=i+j_k} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{i-j_1}{j_2}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-j_1}{j_2+1}}.$$

From 2.10, we know that T_*^{0, j_1} is non-zero only in even degrees and also we know that $T_*^{j_2, j_1} = T^{j_2}(T_*^{0, j_1})$. Therefore $T_{2t+1}^{j_2, j_1} = 0$. $\square$

After we have calculated W_n^k for $k = n - 1, n - 2$, let us now consider the cases for W_n^k when $k = 0, 1$.

Proposition 2.12. Let $t, \ell > 0$, $t \geq \ell$. Then

$$A_s^r \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell}{2\ell}}, & \text{when } r = 2\ell + 1, s = 2t + 1, \\ (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell-1}{2\ell-1}}, & \text{when } r = 2\ell, s = 2t, \text{ and} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof The proof is by induction on r , where the case $r = 2$ is described in [7]. That is, A_{2t}^2 is the $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space with basis $\{v_1 \otimes v_{2t-1}, v_3 \otimes v_{2t-3}, v_5 \otimes v_{2t-5}, \dots, v_{2t-1} \otimes v_1\}$. Therefore $A_{2t}^2 \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^t \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t}{1}}$, and $A_{2t+1}^2 = 0$. Now let us assume that the statement is true for $r = 2\ell$, that is, $A_{2j}^{2\ell} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{j+\ell-1}{2\ell-1}}$ for $j \leq t$. Since $A_*^{2\ell+1} \cong A_* \otimes A_*^{2\ell}$ is an $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space with trivial action of u , then, for $i \geq 0$ and $j \geq \ell$, we have

$$A_{2t+1}^{2\ell+1} \cong \bigoplus_{i+j=t} A_{2i+1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} A_{2j}^{2\ell} \cong \bigoplus_{i+j=t} \mathbb{Z}/2^{i+1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{j+\ell-1}{2\ell-1}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=\ell}^t \binom{j+\ell-1}{2\ell-1}} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell}{2\ell}}.$$

Similarly, for the case $r = 2\ell + 1$, we have $A_{2j+1}^{2\ell+1} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{j+\ell}{2\ell}}$ for $\ell \leq j \leq t$. So, for $i \geq 0$ and $j \geq \ell$, we have

$$A_{2t+2}^{2\ell+2} \cong \bigoplus_{i+j=t} A_{2i+1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} A_{2j+1}^{2\ell+1} \cong \bigoplus_{i+j=t} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{j+\ell}{2\ell}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=\ell}^t \binom{j+\ell}{2\ell}} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell+1}{2\ell+1}}.$$

Finally, let us consider the case when r is odd and s is even or conversely. Since $A_*^r = \overbrace{A_* \otimes A_* \otimes \dots \otimes A_*}^{r \text{ times}}$, for $s \geq r$, we have $A_s^r = \bigoplus_{s=2 \sum_{k=1}^r i_k+r} A_{2i_1+1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} A_{2i_2+1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} \dots \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} A_{2i_r+1}$. This asserts that r is associated with s , in the sense that both should be odd or even, and otherwise $A_s^r = 0$. □

Lemma 2.13. Let $t, \ell > 0, t \geq \ell + 1$. Then

$$T(A_*^r)_s \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell}{2\ell+1}}, & \text{when } r = 2\ell + 1, s = 2t + 1, \\ (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell-1}{2\ell}}, & \text{when } r = 2\ell, s = 2t, \text{ and} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

(Note that $T(A_*^r)_* = T_*^{j_r, j_{r-1}, \dots, j_1}$, where $j_i = 1$ for $i = r$ and other j_k are zero).

Proof We will calculate $T(A_*^{2\ell})_{2t}$. The other cases are similar. Let us start from the free resolution of A_* , which is described in 2.5, then applying $(A_*^{2\ell} \otimes -)$ and shifting by (-1) allows us to calculate $T(A_*^{2\ell})_*$. Since $A_*^{2\ell}$ is an $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space with trivial action of u , see 2.8, then

$$T(A_*^{2\ell})_* = \ker(I \otimes d) = A_*^{2\ell} \otimes \bigoplus_{j_i > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_k} \rangle$$

where $I = id_{A_*^{2\ell}}$ and $d : \bigoplus_{j_k > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_k} \rangle \rightarrow \bigoplus_{j_k > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle b_{j_k} \rangle$ is described in 2.5. Therefore, by 2.12 for $i \geq \ell$ and by 1.2(ii), we have

$$T(A_*^{2\ell})_{2t} = \bigoplus_{t=i+j_k} A_{2i}^{2\ell} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} \mathbb{Z} \langle a_{j_k} \rangle = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{i=\ell}^{t-1} \binom{i+\ell-1}{2\ell-1}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell-1}{2\ell}}.$$

□

By 2.12 and 2.13, we can check that $A_*^{2\ell}[-1] \cong T(A_*^{2\ell-1})$ and $A_*^{2\ell+1}[-1] \cong T(A_*^{2\ell})$.

Corollary 2.14. Let $t, \ell > 0$, and $s \geq r + 3$. Then

$$(A_*^r \otimes T_*^1)_s \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell-1}{r}}, & \text{when } r = 2\ell + 1, s = 2t, \\ 0, & \text{or } r = 2\ell, s = 2t + 1, \text{ and} \\ & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

(Note that $A_*^r \otimes T_*^1 = T_*^{j_{r+1}, j_r, \dots, j_1}$, where $j_i = 1$ for $i = 1$ and other j_k are zero).

Proof We will consider the case $r = 2\ell + 1$ and $s = 2t$. The other cases are similar. From 2.6, 2.12 and 1.2(ii), for $i \geq \ell$ and $j \geq 1$ we have

$$(A_*^r \otimes T_*^1)_{2t} = \oplus_{t=i+j+1} (A_{2i+1}^{2\ell+1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} T_{2j+1}^1) \cong \oplus_{t=i+j+1} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{i+\ell}{2\ell}} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{i=\ell}^{t-2} \binom{i+\ell}{2\ell}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+\ell-1}{2\ell+1}}$$

By 2.12 and 2.14, for $r > 0$, we can check the following.

Corollary 2.15. Let $r > 0$, then

$$A_*^r \otimes T_*^1 \cong A_*^{r+1}[-2].$$

Definition 2.16. Given $j_i \in \mathbb{N}_0$ for $i \geq 1$, we define $\beta_{i,n} = \sum_{k=i}^n j_k$. (of course, $\beta_{i,n}$ depend on $j_1, \dots, j_n$, but the sequence will be clear from the context.)

Corollary 2.17. Let $n > 1$, then

$$T^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} = T^{0, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} \otimes X_*^{\beta_{n,n}}[-\beta_{n,n}]$$

where $X_* = \oplus_{j_k > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_k} \rangle$, that is, $X_{2s-1} = \mathbb{Z}_2 \{u^m a_{j_k} : s = m + j_k\}$.

Proof The proof follows from $T_*^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} = \overbrace{T(T \dots T(T_*^{0, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1})_* \dots)_*}_{j_n \text{ times}}$, and the fact that $T_*^{0, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1}$ is an $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space with trivial action of u . So $T_*^{1, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} = T(T_*^{0, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1})_* = T_*^{0, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} \otimes X_*[-1]$ and $T_*^{2, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} = T(T_*^{1, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1}) = T_*^{0, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} \otimes X_*^2[-2]$. Therefore inductively on n we get the required result.

Proposition 2.18. Let $r_1 \geq 0, r_2 > 1$ and $s \geq r_1 + r_2 + 2$. Then

$$(A_*^{r_1} \otimes T(A_*^{r_2})_*)_s \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+k}{r_1+r_2}}, & \text{when } s = 2t + 1, r_1 + r_2 = 2k + 1, \\ (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+k-1}{r_1+r_2}}, & \text{when } s = 2t, r_1 + r_2 = 2k, \text{ and} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

(Note that $A_*^{r_1} \otimes T(A_*^{r_2})_* = T_*^{j_{r_2+r_1}, \dots, j_{r_2}, \dots, j_1}$ where $j_i = 1$ for $i = r_2$ and other j_k are zero.)

Proof Let us consider the above graded group in degree $s = 2t$. The other cases are similar. By 2.12 and 2.13, for $i \geq \ell_1$ and $j \geq \ell_2 + 1$, we have

$$(A_*^{r_1} \otimes T(A_*^{r_2})_*)_{2t} = \begin{cases} \oplus_{t=i+j} A_{2i}^{2\ell_1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} T(A_*^{2\ell_2})_{2j}, & \text{when } r_1 = 2\ell_1, r_2 = 2\ell_2, \\ \oplus_{t=i+j+1} A_{2i+1}^{2\ell_1+1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} T(A_*^{2\ell_2+1})_{2j+1}, & \text{when } r_1 = 2\ell_1 + 1, r_2 = 2\ell_2 + 1. \end{cases}$$

$$\cong \begin{cases} \oplus_{t=i+j} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{i+\ell_1-1}{2\ell_1-1} \binom{j+\ell_2-1}{2\ell_2}}, & \text{when } r_1 = 2\ell_1, r_2 = 2\ell_2, \\ \oplus_{t=i+j+1} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{i+\ell_1}{2\ell_1} \binom{j+\ell_2}{2\ell_2+1}}, & \text{when } r_1 = 2\ell_1 + 1, r_2 = 2\ell_2 + 1. \end{cases}$$

Then, for $r_1 = 2\ell_1$ and $r_2 = 2\ell_2$, 1.2(iii) shows that

$$\sum_{t=i+j} \binom{i+\ell_1-1}{2\ell_1-1} \binom{j+\ell_2-1}{2\ell_2} = \sum_{m=2\ell_1-1}^{t+\ell_1+\ell_2-2} \binom{m}{2\ell_1-1} \binom{t+\ell_1+\ell_2-2-m}{2\ell_2} = \binom{t+k-1}{r_1+r_2},$$

where $2k = r_1 + r_2$. And similarly, for $r_1 = 2\ell_1 + 1, r_2 = 2\ell_2 + 1$ and $2k = r_1 + r_2$

$$\sum_{t=i+j+1} \binom{i+\ell_1}{2\ell_1} \binom{j+\ell_2}{2\ell_2+1} = \binom{t+\ell_1+\ell_2}{2\ell_1+2\ell_2+2} = \binom{t+k-1}{r_1+r_2}.$$

Examples 2.19. For $r_1 + r_2 = 5$, and $t \geq 3$, we can calculate that

$$T(A_*^5)_{2t+1} = (A_* \otimes T(A_*^4))_{2t+1} = (A_*^2 \otimes T(A_*^3))_{2t+1} = (A_*^3 \otimes T(A_*^2))_{2t+1} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+2}{5}}.$$

And for $r_1 + r_2 = 6$, and $t \geq 4$, we can calculate that

$$T(A_*^6)_{2t} = (A_* \otimes T(A_*^5))_{2t} = (A_*^2 \otimes T(A_*^4))_{2t} = (A_*^3 \otimes T(A_*^3))_{2t} = (A_*^4 \otimes T(A_*^2))_{2t} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+2}{6}}.$$

By 2.6 we know that $T_*^{j_1}$ is concentrated in odd degrees $s \geq 2j_1 + 1$, whereas 2.11 shows that $T_*^{j_2, j_1}$ is concentrated in even degrees $s \geq 2j_1 + 2j_2 + 2$. Similarly to these two cases we can see that $T_*^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1}$ is concentrated in odd degrees $s \geq 2\beta_{1,n} + n$ if n is odd, and in even degrees if n is even. This means $T_*^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1}$ is non-zero just in degrees $s \geq 2\beta_{1,n} + n$ where s and n both are odd or both are even.

By all the previous calculations, we can deduce the next proposition, which is about the calculation of $T_*^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1}$ as a graded group, for any $n > 0$, and using this we can calculate W_n^r for any $0 \leq r \leq n - 1$.

Proposition 2.20. Let $n > 1$. Then, using the notation of 2.16,

$$T_s^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{s+n-2-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+n-1}},$$

for $s \geq 2\beta_{1,n} + n$.

Proof If $j_k = 0$, for all $k \geq 1$, then the left hand side is A_*^n , which is considered in 2.12 and agrees with the above result. And if there is only one k such that $j_k \neq 0$, then the left hand side has the form $A_*^{n-k} \otimes T^{j_k}(A_*^k)_*$, which can be calculated by 2.6, 2.12 and 2.18. Now, if there are at least k_1, k_2 such that j_{k_1} and j_{k_2} are not zero, then in this case we need to use induction on n to calculate the above graded group, where the case $n = 2$ is considered in 2.11. Let us assume that the statement is true for n where $T_*^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1}$ is concentrated in odd degrees. Since

$$T_*^{j_{n+1}, j_n, \dots, j_1} = T_*^{0, j_n, \dots, j_1} \otimes X_*^{\beta_{n+1, n+1}}[-\beta_{n+1, n+1}],$$

see 2.17, where $X_* = \bigoplus_{j_i > 0} \mathbb{Z}_2[u] \langle a_{j_i} \rangle$ and

$$T_{2t}^{0, j_n, \dots, j_1} = \bigoplus_{t=k+s+1} A_{2k+1} \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}} T_{2s+1}^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} \cong \bigoplus_{t=k+s+1} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{2s+1+n-2-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+n-1}},$$

for $k \geq 0$ and $s \geq \beta_{1,n} + \frac{n-1}{2}$. That is, by 1.2(ii),

$$T_{2t}^{j_n, \dots, j_1} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{s=\beta_{1,n}+\frac{n-1}{2}}^{t-1} \binom{2s+n-1-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+n-1}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{2t+n-1-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+n}}.$$

Then, for $2t \geq 2\beta_{1,n+1} + n + 1$, $i_r \geq \beta_{1,n} + \frac{n+1}{2} + r - 1$ and $m_r > 0$ where $1 \leq r \leq j_{n+1}$, we get

$$T_{2t}^{j_{n+1}, j_n, \dots, j_1} = \left(\bigoplus_{t=i_{j_{n+1}}+m_{j_{n+1}}} (\dots (\bigoplus_{i_3=i_2+m_2} (\bigoplus_{i_2=i_1+m_1} T_{2i_1}^{0, j_n, \dots, j_1} \otimes X_{2m_1-1})_{2i_2} \otimes X_{2m_2-1})_{2i_3} \dots)_{2i_{j_{n+1}}} \otimes X_{2m_{j_{n+1}}-1})_{2t} \right)$$

where the right hand side isomorphic to

$$\bigoplus_{t=i_{j_{n+1}}+m_{j_{n+1}}} \dots \bigoplus_{i_3=i_2+m_2} \bigoplus_{i_2=i_1+m_1} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{2i_1+n-1-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+n}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^D$$

and

$$D = \sum_{i_{j_{n+1}}=\beta_{1,n}+\frac{n+1}{2}+j_{n+1}-1}^{t-1} \cdots \sum_{i_2=\beta_{1,n}+\frac{n+1}{2}+1}^{i_3-1} \sum_{i_1=\beta_{1,n}+\frac{n+1}{2}}^{i_2-1} \binom{\frac{2i_1+n-1}{2}-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+n}.$$

By 1.2(ii), we have

$$\sum_{i_1=\beta_{1,n}+\frac{n+1}{2}}^{i_2-1} \binom{\frac{2i_1+n-1}{2}-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+n} = \binom{\frac{2i_2+n-1}{2}-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+1+n}$$

and

$$\sum_{i_2=\beta_{1,n}+\frac{n+1}{2}+1}^{i_3-1} \binom{\frac{2i_2+n-1}{2}-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+1+n} = \binom{\frac{2i_3+n-1}{2}-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+2+n}.$$

Therefore we can deduce that

$$D = \sum_{i_{j_{n+1}}=\beta_{1,n}+\frac{n+1}{2}+j_{n+1}-1}^{t-1} \binom{\frac{2i_{j_{n+1}}+n-1}{2}-j_1}{\beta_{2,n}+j_{n+1}-1+n} = \binom{\frac{2t+n-1}{2}-j_1}{\beta_{2,n+1}+n} = \binom{\frac{s+(n+1)-2}{2}-j_1}{\beta_{2,n+1}+n}$$

where $s = 2t \geq 2\beta_{1,n+1} + n + 1$.

□

Now we have calculated the summands of W_n^r as groups. In the next theorem we will deal with the results in [6, Lemma 3.4], together with the Künneth sequence for P_n , to explain that there is no extension problem for this Künneth sequence, for any finite number n not just for $n = 2$ and therefore the middle term of this sequence is a direct sum of the left and the right side. From this we will decompose $bu_*(P_n)$ as a direct sum of W_n^r , for $0 \leq r \leq n - 1$.

Theorem 2.21. Let $n \geq 1$. Then

$$bu_*(P_n) = \bigoplus_{r=0}^{n-1} W_n^r.$$

Proof The proof is by induction on n . Let us start from the Künneth short exact sequence for P_n ,

$$0 \rightarrow A_* \otimes bu_*(P_{n-1}) \rightarrow bu_*(P_n) \rightarrow T(bu_*(P_{n-1})) \rightarrow 0,$$

and consider the case $n = 3$. The case $n = 2$ was already considered in [7] and there is no extension problem for the Künneth sequence when $n = 2$ because the left hand side is non-zero only in even degrees, whereas the right side is non-zero only in odd degrees. Therefore

$$bu_*(P_2) \cong A_*^2 \oplus T(A_*) = T_*^{0,0} \oplus T_*^1 = W_2^0 \oplus W_2^1.$$

For $n = 3$, the analogous Künneth sequence has the form

$$0 \rightarrow T_*^{0,0,0} \oplus T_*^{0,1} \rightarrow bu_*(P_3) \rightarrow T_*^{1,0} \oplus T_*^2 \rightarrow 0.$$

Now 2.12 and 2.14 show that

$$(T_*^{0,0,0} \oplus T_*^{0,1})_s \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-1}{1}}, & \text{when } s = 2t, t \geq 2, \\ (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+1}{2}}, & \text{when } s = 2t + 1, t \geq 1, \text{ and} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Whereas 2.13 and 2.6 show that

$$(T_*^{1,0} \oplus T_*^2)_s \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t}{2}}, & \text{when } s = 2t, t \geq 2, \\ \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-1}, & \text{when } s = 2t + 1, t \geq 2, \text{ and} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Therefore $bu_i(P_3) = 0$ for $i < 3$, $bu_3(P_3) \cong \mathbb{Z}/2$ and for $t \geq 2$, we have exact sequences

$$0 \rightarrow (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-1}{1}} \rightarrow bu_{2t}(P_3) \rightarrow (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t}{2}} \rightarrow 0,$$

and

$$0 \rightarrow (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+1}{2}} \rightarrow bu_{2t+1}(P_3) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-1} \rightarrow 0.$$

By [6, Lemma 3.4], we have

$$bu_{2t}(P_3) \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^1 \binom{j}{0} \binom{t+j-1}{j+1}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-1}{1} + \binom{t}{2}}$$

and

$$bu_{2t+1}(P_3) \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-1} \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^1 \binom{j}{1} \binom{t+j}{j+1}} = \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-1} \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t+1}{2}}.$$

Thus the above calculations tell us that there are no extension problems in the Künneth sequence. Therefore

$$bu_*(P_3) \cong T_*^{0,0,0} \oplus T_*^{0,1} \oplus T_*^{1,0} \oplus T_*^2 = \bigoplus_{r=0}^2 W_3^r,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} W_3^0 &= A_*^3 = T_*^{0,0,0}, \\ W_3^1 &= (A_* \otimes T(A_*))_* \oplus T(A_*^2)_* = T_*^{0,1} \oplus T_*^{1,0}, \text{ and} \\ W_3^2 &= T^2(A_*)_* = T_*^2. \end{aligned}$$

Now, let us assume that there is no extension problem for the above Künneth sequence for $n = 2n_1$, and the statement is true in this case. And let us start again from the Künneth sequence,

$$0 \rightarrow A_* \otimes bu_*(P_{2n_1}) \rightarrow bu_*(P_{2n_1+1}) \rightarrow T(bu_*(P_{2n_1})) \rightarrow 0$$

where

$$bu_{2t}(P_{2n_1+1}) = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i} \binom{t-2n_1+j+i+1}{j+1}},$$

for $t \geq n_1 + 1$.

By 2.8, $A_* \otimes bu_*(P_{2n_1})$ is an $\mathbb{F}_2$ -vector space with trivial action of u , where, by [6, Lemma 3.4], we have

$$bu_{2t+1}(P_{2n_1}) = \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-2n_1+2} \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-2} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{t-2n_1+j+i+3}{j+1}}$$

and $\mathbb{Z}/2^{t-2n_1+2}$ comes from the only summand $T_{2t+1}^{2n_1-1}$ of $bu_*(P_{2n_1})_{2t}$ which consists of a higher 2-torsion group with non-trivial action of u . Then, by 2.10 for $m \geq n_1$ and $\ell \geq 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (A_* \otimes bu_*(P_{2n_1}))_{2t} &\cong (A_* \otimes T_*^{2n_1-1})_{2t} \oplus \bigoplus_{\ell=m+1}^t A_{2\ell+1} \otimes (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-2} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{m-2n_1+j+i+3}{j+1}} \\ &= (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{t-2n_1+1} \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{m=n_1}^{t-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-2} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{m-2n_1+j+i+3}{j+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

In the other side of the sequence, for $t \geq n_1 + 1$, $m \geq n_1$ and $k > 0$, we have

$$T(bu_*(P_{2n_1}))_{2t} = \bigoplus_{t=m+k}^t bu_{2m}(P_{2n_1}) \otimes X_{2k-1},$$

where $X_{2k-1} = \mathbb{Z}\{u^m a_{\ell_i} : k = m + \ell_i, \text{ and } a_{\ell_i} \text{ of degree } 2\ell_i - 1\}$. Then [6, Lemma 3.4] shows that

$$\begin{aligned} T(bu_*(P_{2n_1}))_{2t} &\cong \bigoplus_{t=m+k} (\mathbb{Z}/2) \sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{m-2n_1+j+i+2}{j+1} \\ &= (\mathbb{Z}/2) \sum_{m=n_1}^{t-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i} \binom{m-2n_1+j+i+2}{j+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Inductively on t and n_1 , we can see that

$$\begin{aligned} t - 2n_1 + 1 + \sum_{m=n_1}^{t-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-2} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{m-2n_1+j+i+3}{j+1} \\ + \sum_{m=n_1}^{t-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i} \binom{m-2n_1+j+i+2}{j+1} = \sum_{j=0}^{2n_1-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i} \binom{t-2n_1+j+i+1}{j+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$bu_{2t}(P_{2n_1+1}) \cong (A_* \otimes bu_*(P_{2n_1}))_{2t} \oplus T(bu_*(P_{2n_1}))_{2t}.$$

Similarly, we can deduce the same result for degree $2t + 1$. This yields that there is no extension problem in the Künneth sequence for P_{2n_1+1} , so $bu_*(P_{2n_1+1}) \cong (A_* \otimes bu_*(P_{2n_1})) \oplus T(bu_*(P_{2n_1}))$. By 3.5, we have

$$\bigoplus_{r=0}^{2n_1} W_{2n_1+1}^r = \bigoplus_{r=0}^{2n_1} (A_* \otimes W_{2n_1}^r \oplus T(W_{2n_1}^{r-1})) = \bigoplus_{r=0}^{2n_1-1} (A_* \otimes W_{2n_1}^r \oplus T(W_{2n_1}^r))$$

where the right side is equal to $(A_* \otimes bu_*(P_{2n_1})) \oplus T(bu_*(P_{2n_1}))$. Thus $bu_*(P_{2n_1+1}) = \bigoplus_{r=0}^{2n_1} W_{2n_1+1}^r$.

Similarly, if we assume the result for $n = 2n_1 + 1$, a similar calculation shows that there is no non-trivial extension in the Künneth sequence for P_{2n_1+2} , that is, $bu_*(P_{2n_1+2}) \cong (A_* \otimes bu_*(P_{2n_1+1})) \oplus T(bu_*(P_{2n_1+1}))$, and again 3.5 gives the required result for $2n_1 + 2$. Thus

$$bu_*(P_{2n_1+2}) = \bigoplus_{r=0}^{2n_1+1} W_{2n_1+2}^r.$$

□

Remark 2.22. Each W_n^r has $\binom{n-1}{r}$ summands, which gives the total number of summands of $bu_*(P_n)$ to be $\sum_{r=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{r} = 2^{n-1}$.

Example 2.23. For $n = 5$, we have $bu_*(P_5) = \bigoplus_{r=0}^4 W_5^r$, where

$$\begin{aligned} W_5^0 &= T_*^{0,0,0,0,0} \\ W_5^1 &= T_*^{1,0,0,0} \oplus T_*^{0,1,0,0} \oplus T_*^{0,0,1,0} \oplus T_*^{0,0,0,1} \\ W_5^2 &= T_*^{2,0,0} \oplus T_*^{0,2,0} \oplus T_*^{0,0,2} \oplus T_*^{1,1,0} \oplus T_*^{1,0,1} \oplus T_*^{0,1,1} \\ W_5^3 &= T_*^{3,0} \oplus T_*^{2,1} \oplus T_*^{1,2} \oplus T_*^{0,3}, \text{ and} \\ W_5^4 &= T_*^4. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $bu_*(P_5)$ has $2^4 = 16$ summands. In degree $2t$, we have $W_5^0 = W_5^2 = W_5^4 = 0$, whereas

$$W_5^1 = T_{2t}^{1,0,0,0} \oplus T_{2t}^{0,1,0,0} \oplus T_{2t}^{0,0,1,0} \oplus T_{2t}^{0,0,0,1} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{3\binom{t+1}{4} + \binom{t}{3}} \text{ and}$$

$$W_5^3 \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t}{4} + \binom{t-1}{3} + \binom{t-2}{2} + \binom{t-3}{1}},$$

so $bu_{2t}(P_5) \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^3 \sum_{i=0}^1 \binom{j}{2i} \binom{t+j+i-3}{j+1}}$ and this result agrees with the result in [6, Lemma 3.4]. Similarly, in degree $2t + 1$ we have $W_5^1 = W_5^3 = 0$ whereas

$$W_5^0 = T_{2t+1}^{0,0,0,0} \cong (\mathbb{Z})^{\binom{t+2}{4}}$$

$$W_5^2 = T_{2t+1}^{2,0,0} \oplus T_{2t+1}^{0,2,0} \oplus T_{2t+1}^{0,0,2} \oplus T_{2t+1}^{1,1,0} \oplus T_{2t+1}^{1,0,1} \oplus T_{2t+1}^{0,1,1} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{3\binom{t+1}{4} + \binom{t-1}{2} + 2\binom{t}{3}} \text{ and}$$

$$W_5^4 = T_{2t+1}^4 \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-3}.$$

Thus $bu_{2t+1}(P_5) \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-3} \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^3 \sum_{i=0}^1 \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{t+j+i-2}{j+1}}$ and this result also agrees with the result in [6, Lemma 3.4].

3. Tor decomposition of $bu_{p^*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$

3.1. In 1972, Holzsager [3] split the space $\Sigma B\mathbb{Z}/p$ with p -adic coefficients into the wedge of $p - 1$ spaces B_i , where B_i has homology only in dimensions $2k(p - 1) + 2i$, for all natural numbers k . So the spectrum $\Sigma^\infty B\mathbb{Z}/p$ splits as $\Sigma^\infty B\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^\infty B_i$, see also [4]. Here the spectrum B_i has stable cells in dimension $2k(p - 1) + 2i - \epsilon$, for $\epsilon = 0, 1$ such that $2k(p - 1) + 2i - \epsilon \geq 0$. The splitting of $B\mathbb{Z}/p$ as a spectrum is also written as $B\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} B_i$.

By [5], for the case $E = lu$ the Adams summand and $X = B\mathbb{Z}/p$, we have the Thom isomorphism $lu_{q+2}(T(\xi)) \cong lu_q(B\mathbb{Z}/p)$, that is, $lu_*(T(\xi)) \cong lu_*(\Sigma^2 B\mathbb{Z}/p)$. This isomorphism is induced by a homotopy equivalence $lu \wedge T(\xi) \simeq lu \wedge \Sigma^2 B\mathbb{Z}/p$. By applying the splitting of $B\mathbb{Z}/p$ and substituting $T(\xi) = \frac{B\mathbb{Z}/p}{B^1}$ in this homotopy equivalence we get

$$lu \wedge (B_1 \vee B_2 \vee \cdots \vee B_{p-1}) / (B^1) \simeq lu \wedge \Sigma^2 (B_1 \vee B_2 \vee \cdots \vee B_{p-1}).$$

Both sides of the last equivalence are wedges of $p - 1$ pieces, and by comparing the dimensions of bottom cells we deduce the following homotopy equivalence $lu \wedge \Sigma^2 B_i \simeq lu \wedge B_{i+1}$ for $1 \leq i < p - 1$. Inductively on i , we get $lu \wedge \Sigma^{2(i-1)} B_1 \simeq lu \wedge B_i$.

It would be more interesting if we can carrying on for any prime p using the splitting $bu_p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i-2} lu$ and the Holzsager splitting $B\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} B_i$ to decompose $bu_{p^*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$ as a direct sum of some graded groups. This decomposition agreed with the result in [6, Theorem 3.8] and both yield that there is no extension problems in the Künneth sequence for $bu_{p^*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$.

The purpose of this section is the composition of $lu_*(B_1)^n$ first and using the above splitting to deduce the composition of $bu_{p^*}(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$.

Notation 3.2.

- In order to exploit certain splittings of spectra and at the same time to simplify the writing, we will write bu for bu_p , the connective unitary K-theory with p -adic integer coefficients $\mathbb{Z}_p$, where $bu_p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i-2} lu$.
- Here we write A_* for $lu_*(B_1)$.

By the Atiyah-Hirzebruch spectral sequence, see [1], for $X = B_1$ and $E = lu$ we have $lu_j(B_1) = \mathbb{Z}/p^{k+1}$ when $j = 2k(p - 1) + 1$ and it is zero otherwise.

Example 3.3. As in [7, 2.9], for $X = B_1$, the Künneth sequence has the form

$$0 \rightarrow lu_*(B_1) \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]} lu_*(B_1) \rightarrow lu_*(B_1 \wedge B_1) \rightarrow \text{Tor}_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]}^1(lu_*(B_1), lu_*(B_1))[-1] \rightarrow 0.$$

So, in degree $2k(p-1) + 2$, the left-hand side is the graded $\mathbb{F}_p$ -vector space spanned by

$$\{v_1 \otimes v_{2k(p-1)+1}, v_{2(p-1)+1} \otimes v_{2(k-1)(p-1)+1}, \dots, v_{2k(p-1)+1} \otimes v_1\}.$$

which is concentrated in even degrees.

To calculate the graded group $\text{Tor}_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]}^1(lu_*(B_1), lu_*(B_1))[-1]$, we can consider the following free $\mathbb{Z}_p[v]$ -resolution of $lu_{2(p-1)*+1}(B_1)$

$$0 \longrightarrow \bigoplus_{j \geq 0} \mathbb{Z}_p[v] \langle a_{2j(p-1)+1} \rangle \xrightarrow{d} \bigoplus_{j \geq 0} \mathbb{Z}_p[v] \langle b_{2j(p-1)+1} \rangle \xrightarrow{\varepsilon} lu_{2(p-1)*+1}(B_1) \longrightarrow 0$$

where $\varepsilon(b_{2j(p-1)+1}) = v_{2j(p-1)+1}$ for all $j \geq 0$ and $d(a_{2j(p-1)+1}) = pb_{2j(p-1)+1} - vb_{2(j-1)(p-1)+1}$ for $j \geq 0$.

After applying $(lu_{2(p-1)*+1}(B_1) \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]} -)$ to the above resolution, we can calculate

$$\ker(I \otimes d) = \ker(\bigoplus_{j \geq 0} lu_{2(p-1)*+1}(B_1) \langle a_{2j(p-1)+1} \rangle \rightarrow \bigoplus_{j \geq 0} lu_{2(p-1)*+1}(B_1) \langle b_{2j(p-1)+1} \rangle).$$

In degree $2k(p-1) + 2$, this graded group has a generator of the form

$$v_1 \otimes a_{2k(p-1)+1} + v_{2(p-1)+1} \otimes a_{2(k-1)(p-1)+1} + \dots + v_{2k(p-1)+1} \otimes a_1.$$

Since this generator has a summand $v_{2k(p-1)+1}$, so in degree $2k(p-1) + 2$, the group

$$\text{Tor}_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]}^1(lu_{2*+1}(B_1), lu_{2*+1}(B_1))$$

$$\mathbb{Z}/p^k \langle v_1 \otimes a_{2k(p-1)+1} + v_{2(p-1)+1} \otimes a_{2(k-1)(p-1)+1} + \dots + v_{2k(p-1)+1} \otimes a_1 \rangle.$$

So $\text{Tor}_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]}^1(lu_{2*+1}(B_1), lu_{2*+1}(B_1))[-1]$, in degree $2k(p-1) + 3$, is the finite cyclic group of order p^k . this group is concentrated in odd degrees. So the middle group $lu_*(B_1 \wedge B_1)$ in any given degree is isomorphic to the one on the left or the one on the right side.

By applying $T(A_*) \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]} -$ instead of $A_* \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_p[v]} -$ to the previous free resolution of A_* with shifting by (-1) and by using induction on n , we can calculate the graded group T_*^n . This is non-zero just in degrees $2t(p-1) + 2n + 1$.

Proposition 3.4. For $n, t \geq 0$,

$$T_{2t(p-1)+2n+1}^n \cong \mathbb{Z}/p^{t+1} \langle \sum_{i+\sum_{k=1}^n j_k=t} v_{2i(p-1)+1} a_{j_1} a_{j_2} \dots a_{j_n} \rangle,$$

where a_{j_k} is in degree $2j_k(p-1) + 1$.

Definition 3.5. Let $0 \leq k \leq n-1$, we define the weight k iterated T as

$$W_n^k = \bigoplus_{\sum j_i=k} T_*^{j_n-k, j_{n-k-1}, \dots, j_1}$$

where $j_i \in \mathbb{N}_0$, and $T_*^{j_n-k, j_{n-k-1}, \dots, j_1}$ as in 2.3.

Lemma 3.6. Let $0 \leq k \leq n-1$. With the exceptions of A_* and T_*^n , each summand of W_n^k is a graded $\mathbb{F}_p$ -vector space, on which v acts trivially.

By all the previous calculations, we can deduce the next result, which is about the calculation of $T_*^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1}$ as a graded group, which is non-zero just in degrees $2t(p-1) + 2\beta_{1,n} + n$ for $t \geq 0$, and again using this to calculate W_n^r for any $0 \leq r \leq n-1$.

Proposition 3.7. Let $n > 1$. Then, using the notation of 2.16,

$$T_{2t(p-1)+2\beta_{1,n}+n}^{j_n, j_{n-1}, \dots, j_1} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\binom{t+\beta_{2,n}+n-1}{\beta_{2,n}+n-1}}.$$

For $p = 2$, we can get the same result in 2.20. By 3.7, if $j_k = 0$ for all $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, we can calculate the graded group A_*^n which is non-zero just in degrees $2t(p-1) + n$

$$A_{2t(p-1)+n}^n = T_{2t(p-1)+n}^{\overbrace{0, 0, \dots, 0}^{n \text{ times}}} \cong (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\binom{t+n-1}{n-1}}.$$

This result also agree with 2.12 when $p = 2$.

By the splitting $bu \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i-2} lu$, the Holzsauger splitting $B\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} B_i$ and $lu \wedge \Sigma^{2(i-1)} B_1 \simeq lu \wedge B_i$ we have

$$bu \wedge \overbrace{B\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge B\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge \dots \wedge B\mathbb{Z}/p}^{n \text{ times}} \simeq \bigvee_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n+1}=0}^{p-2} \sum_{k=1}^{2\Sigma_{k=1}^{n+1} i_k} lu \wedge \overbrace{B_1 \wedge B_1 \wedge \dots \wedge B_1}^{n \text{ times}}.$$

Applying the homotopy group π_* we get that

$$bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n} \cong \bigoplus_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n+1}=0}^{p-2} lu_{*-2\Sigma_{k=1}^{n+1} i_k} (B_1)^{\wedge n}.$$

Again we have calculated the summands of W_n^r for $lu_*(B_1)$ as graded groups. In the next theorem we will deal with the results in [6, 3.8], together with the Künneth sequence for $lu_*(B_1)$ and using the above discutient to explain that there is no extension problem for this Künneth sequence for $bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$, for any finite number n , and decompose $bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$ as a direct sum of some graded groups. The proof is similar to 3.8, so it is enough to consider some spacial cases as examples.

Theorem 3.8. Let $n \geq 1$. Then

$$bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n} = \bigoplus_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n+1}=0}^{p-2} \bigoplus_{r=0}^{n-1} W_n^r$$

where $W_n^r = \bigoplus_{\Sigma j_i=r} T_{*-2\Sigma_{k=1}^{n+1} i_k}^{j_{n-r}, j_{n-r-1}, \dots, j_1}$.

Example 3.9. For $n = p = 3$, $bu_9(B\mathbb{Z}/3)^{\wedge 3} = \bigoplus_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4=0}^1 \bigoplus_{r=0}^2 W_3^r$ where $W_3^r = \bigoplus_{\Sigma j_i=r} T_{9-2\Sigma_{k=1}^4 i_k}^{j_{3-r}, j_{2-r}, \dots, j_1}$.

By 3.4 and 3.7 we have $bu_9(B\mathbb{Z}/3)^{\wedge 3} = T_9^2 \oplus (T_7^{0,0,0})^4 \oplus (T_5^2)^6 \oplus (T_3^{0,0,0})^4 = \mathbb{Z}/3^2 \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/3)^{22}$. And

by [6, 3.8], we have $bu_9(B\mathbb{Z}/3)^{\wedge 3} = \Gamma(k, 4) \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/3)^{\sum_{j=0}^1 \sum_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{2-j}=0}^1 \binom{j}{j+1} \binom{4+j-\sum_{a=1}^2 \lambda_a}{j+1}} = \mathbb{Z}/3^2 \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/3)^{22}$, where $\Gamma(k, 4) = \mathbb{Z}/3^2 \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/3)^6$ and $(\mathbb{Z}/3)^{\sum_{j=0}^1 \sum_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{2-j}=0}^1 \binom{j}{j+1} \binom{4+j-\sum_{a=1}^2 \lambda_a}{j+1}} = (\mathbb{Z}/3)^{16}$.

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